

Complexing behavior of nucleic acid constituents towards mercuric chloride

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Complexes of Hg^{II} with adenine, guanine, hypoxanthine, uracil, cytosine adenosine and xanthosine have been synthesized and characterized by elemental analysis, IR and ¹H NMR spectral data.

The binding of metal species to nucleic acids may influence various biological functions including those related to structural motifs induced coordinations¹. The present paper discusses the synthesis and characterization of complexes of Hg^{II} with adenine, guanine, hypoxanthine, uracil, cytosine, adenosine and xanthosine. The compounds described represent biologically active complexes in the strict sense containing M-C bond with a bimolecule².

Results and Discussion

Mercury atom in a neutral mercuric halide complex is a typical soft electron pair acceptor and is strongly solvated by Lewis bases³ and of the stability constants of the halides, earlier reported⁴, indicate clearly that only Cl⁻ ion binds with biomolecules.

The analytical and physical data of the white complexes are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Physical and analytical data of complexes*

Compd	M p °C	μ $\Omega^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$	λ_{max} nm
Hg(ade)Cl ₂	275d	702	278
Hg(gua)Cl ₂	360d	397	260
Hg(hypo) ₂ Cl ₄	270d	811	265
Hg(ura) ₂ Cl ₂	275d	453	268
Hg(cyt) ₂ Cl ₄	290d	453	270
Hg(ado) ₂ Cl ₄	195	800	278
Hg(xano) ₂ Cl ₄	300d	550	270

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses

Electronic spectra for the complexes revealed band at 260–280 nm showing the involvement of π - π^* electron transition of the ligand in complex formation.

IR spectra of the adenine complex showed a strong band at 3100 cm⁻¹ (NH). The NH₂ deformation mode shifted to lower frequency by about 40 cm⁻¹ and observed at 1610 cm⁻¹ on coordination to the metal ion. The C=N and C=C stretching frequencies were observed at 1420, 1510 and

1580 cm⁻¹ with the lowering of 20–40 cm⁻¹, which suggests the involvement of ring in coordination to metal ion. This is further supported by the ¹H NMR spectrum (DMSO-*d*₆) where NH₂ protons shifted downfield by about 0.26 ppm and observed at δ 7.35. The C₂-H and C₈-H protons shifted downfield by 0.05 ppm and observed at δ 8.15 and 8.18, respectively, suggesting the involvement of ring nitrogen N(7) and NH₂ for coordination to metal ion.

IR spectra of the guanine complex showed a band at 3100–3300 cm⁻¹ (N-H and C-H). The NH₂ deformation was observed at 1650 cm⁻¹, which shifted to lower frequency by about 50 cm⁻¹ indicating the involvement of exocyclic oxygen in coordination. The C=N and C=C stretching frequencies shifted to lower frequency by about 10–20 cm⁻¹ and was observed at 1360, 1450 and 1500 cm⁻¹, which supports the involvement of ring nitrogen in the coordination and also forming the chelate structure through C₆=O and N(7) for the guanine complex; this is further supported by the ¹H NMR spectra. In guanine base the C₈-H proton resonance peak, observed at δ 7.50, shifted downfield by 0.12 ppm in the complex and observed at δ 7.62, which supports the chelate structure in guanine complex.

IR spectrum of the hypoxanthine complex showed the N-H, C-H stretch at 3020–2400 cm⁻¹. The C=O stretching frequency did not shift and was observed at 1670 cm⁻¹ as in the ligand, and the C=N and C=C stretching frequencies shifted downfield by about 15–60 cm⁻¹, indicating the involvement of ring nitrogen in coordination. This is further supported by ¹H NMR spectra of the complex in which C₂-H and C₈-H proton resonance peaks shifted down by 0.06 and 0.10 ppm and were observed at δ 8.02 and 8.20, respectively; as C₈-H proton shifted more than C₂-H the coordination to metal can be proposed at N(7).

IR spectra of the uracil complex showed a broad band at 2200–2800 cm⁻¹ (N-H and C-H). The C₂=O stretching fre-

quency was observed in same region of ligand, whereas $C_4=O$ stretching frequency was lowered by 60 cm^{-1} , indicating the involvement of ring nitrogen in coordination. In ^1H NMR spectrum of uracil, two doublets centered at δ 5.44 and 7.38 are assigned to $C_5\text{-H}$ and $C_6\text{-H}$ protons and in complex there was negligible shift of these protons which supports the involvement of $C=O$ group in coordination. Metal binding sites in 1-methyluracil and uridine is N(3) of ring nitrogen and deprotonation of this site at $pK_a = 9.8$ observed via N(3), O(4) or N(3), O(4), O(2) gave a clear evidence for exclusive metal binding through exocyclic oxygen of neutral base⁵. Displacement of proton at N(3) position of uracil or thiamine nucleobases by metal ion increases the basicity of adjacent exocyclic oxygen, thereby allowing additional metal ion or proton to bind to this site⁶.

IR spectrum of the cytosine complex showed similar peaks for $C=O$, $C=C$ and $C=N$ as in ligand. The NH_2 deformation mode shifted downfield by about 20 cm^{-1} and appeared as medium broad band at $1620\text{--}1645\text{ cm}^{-1}$. ^1H NMR spectra of cytosine showed two doublets for $C_5\text{-H}$ and $C_6\text{-H}$ at δ 5.56 and 7.31, respectively, and in the complex it was observed at δ 5.84 and 7.55, respectively. The NH_2 proton shifted downfield by 0.8 ppm. $C_5\text{-H}$ and $C_6\text{-H}$ deflected very less compared to NH_2 , so NH_2 is presumed to be the binding site.

IR spectra of the adenosine complex show a broad band at $3100\text{--}3300\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (N-H). The NH_2 deformation mode shifted down by about 60 cm^{-1} showing the involvement of NH_2 group in coordination. In ^1H NMR spectra of the complex, the NH_2 protons shifted downfield by about 0.10 ppm and was observed at δ 7.42, which suggests, the participation of NH_2 group in the coordination.

IR spectra of the xanthosine complex showed the reduction of $C=C$ and $C=N$ stretching frequencies by about $50\text{--}120\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and was observed at 1660 and 1560 cm^{-1} , showing the involvement of ring nitrogen in coordination. In ^1H NMR spectra of the complex, the $C_8\text{-H}$ proton resonance peak shifted downfield by 0.99 ppm and was observed at δ 7.99, suggesting the involvement of N(7) of the ring in coordination.

Experimental

Chromatographically pure nucleobases (Sigma) and

mercuric chloride (excel IR) were used. C, H and N were analyzed at C.S.M.C.R.I., Bhavanagar, Gujarat. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 1600 FTIR spectrophotometer, electronic spectra on a Shimadzu UV 240 spectrophotometer and ^1H NMR spectra on a 200 MHz spectrometer, recorded at I.I.C.T., Hyderabad. A Digisun DI 909 conductivity meter was used to measure the conductivity of the complex in $\text{DMSO}/\text{CH}_3\text{COOH}$.

A mixture of 1 mM aqueous metal solution and 1 mM adenine solution (in alcohol) was kept overnight at 0° . The resulting white solid was washed with ice-cold water and ethanol and dried in a vacuum. A mixture of 1 mM aqueous metal solution and 1m M guanine solution (in hot 1 N HCl) was refluxed for 1 h at 130° and kept overnight at 0° . The resulting white solid was washed with ice-cold water and ethanol and dried in a vacuum. A mixture of 1m M aqueous metal solution and 1 mM hypoxanthine solution (in hot 1 : 1 mixture of alcohol and water) was heated on water-bath for 2 h, then concentrated and kept overnight at 0° . The resulting white solid was washed with ice-cold water and ethanol and dried in a vacuum. A mixture of 1 mM aqueous metal solution and 1m M uracil/cytosine solution (in excess hot alcohol) was refluxed for 3 h on a water-bath, then kept overnight at 0° . The resulting white solid was washed with ice-cold water and ethanol and dried in a vacuum. A mixture of 1 mM aqueous metal solution (pH adjusted to 3 with 0.1 N HCl) and 1 mM aqueous adenosine/xanthosine solution (pH adjusted to around 5 with 1 N HCl) was refluxed on a water-bath at 130° , then kept overnight at 0° . The resulting white solid was washed with ice-cold water and ethanol and dried in a vacuum.

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